

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of DL-methionine by Keggin-type 12-tungstocobaltate(III) in aqueous acetic acid medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of the reaction of DL-methionine with 12-tungstocobaltate(III) has been studied over the range of $8.4 \leq 10^4$ [DL-methionine] ≤ 14.0 , $3.0 \leq \text{pH} \leq 5.0$ and $20 \leq T \leq 35$ °C in aqueous acetic acid medium. The electron transfer reaction showed first-order dependence each in [DL-methionine]_T and [12-tungstocobaltate(III)]_T. The main product of the reaction was found to be methionine sulfoxide. The activation parameters of the redox reaction were found to be $\Delta H^\ddagger = 106 \pm 3$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = 75.7 \pm 10$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively. High positive value of ΔS^\ddagger indicates the reaction to be outer sphere.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, heteropoly acids, DL-methionine, redox reaction.

The Keggin-type 12-tungstocobaltate(III) (Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻ or Co^{III}W) cluster has a reduction potential ($E_{\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{W}} = 1.0$ V)¹. Such clusters are known for photochemical hydrogen generation and are involved in multi-electron reduction processes²⁻⁴. The redox reactions of Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻ has been recently reviewed^{5,6}. The kinetics of the oxidation of a number of inorganic compounds such as thiourea⁷, thiocyanate⁸, iodide⁸, antimony(III)⁹, platinum(II)¹⁰, arsenous acid¹¹ and organic compounds such as thiols^{12,13}, ascorbic acid¹⁴, hydroquinone¹⁴, catechol¹⁴, glutathione¹⁵, formate¹⁶, citric acid¹⁷ in acidic medium are reported^{7,18}. These electron transfer processes are found to be outer sphere.

The sulphur containing amino acids and peptide oxidation reactions are studied mostly for their biochemical importance^{19,20}. Methionine is one of the important amino acids which undergoes biochemical redox processes involving the oxidation of the sulphur atom to sulfoxide. Strong oxidants such as Cr(VI)^{21,22} oxidises methionine to sulfoxide and subsequently to sulfone followed by total oxidation of the molecule, however other oxidants such as iron-thiolate²⁰ and peroxyxynitrite²³ oxidises methionine to sulfoxide.

In order to examine the redox behavior of 12-tungstocobaltate(III), its reaction with DL-methionine has been investigated. The main product of the redox reaction has been isolated and characterised.

Results and discussion

The Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻ has absorbance maxima at 388 nm and on mixing with DL-methionine the peak is found to decrease with time (Fig. 1)¹¹ with a simultaneous increase of a new

and comparatively weak peak at 624 nm due to the formation of Co^{II}W₁₂O₄₀⁶⁻. So the decrease of absorbance at 390 nm is followed for the reduction of Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻ by DL-methionine in all the kinetic runs for studying the effect of various parameters such as [Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻], [DL-methionine], % acetic acid, pH and temperature.

Table 1. Kinetic data for the electron transfer reaction between Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻ and DL-methionine at 30 °C

10^4 [Co ^{III} W ₁₂ O ₄₀ ⁵⁻] _T (mol dm ⁻³)	10^3 [DL-methionine] _T (mol dm ⁻³)	Acetic acid % (v/v)	pH	10^4 k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
2.8	8.4	0	4.5	5.25
2.8	9.8	0	4.5	6.02
2.8	11.2	0	4.5	6.61
2.8	12.6	0	4.5	7.24
2.8	14.0	0	4.5	7.94
5.6	14.0	0	4.5	7.83
8.4	14.0	0	4.5	8.00
2.8	8.4	10	4.5	5.50
2.8	8.4	20	4.5	6.08
2.8	8.4	30	4.5	6.56
2.8	8.4	40	4.5	7.10
2.8	2.8	0	3.0	2.27
2.8	2.8	0	3.5	2.23
2.8	2.8	0	4.0	2.30
2.8	2.8	0	4.5	2.45
2.8	2.8	0	5.0	2.37

Effect of [Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻] on reaction rate : In the first set of kinetic experiments, [Co^{III}W₁₂O₄₀⁵⁻]_T (T = total) was varied at fixed [DL-methionine] = 14.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³. The pH and temperature were kept constant. The pseudo-first-order plots were linear ($R^2 = 0.99$) in each case giving

$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) = 7.92 ± 0.1 (Table 1) and showing that the reaction is first-order in $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]_{\text{T}}$. The independence of k_{obs} at 30°C under the conditions $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}} = 14.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$ over a $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]_{\text{T}}$ range from 2.8×10^{-4} to $8.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ is in agreement with first-order dependence on $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]_{\text{T}}$. The rate law therefore is given by

$$\text{Rate} = -d[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} \quad (1)$$

Effect of pH on reaction rate : Under the conditions of 30°C , $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the pH was varied from 3.0 to 5.0 and the k_{obs} were found to be fairly constant at $(2.32 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Table 1). The reaction does not show any $[\text{H}^+]$ dependence in the above pH range. In the above pH range the reductant remains in the neutral form (HA, Fig. 3A). However, at higher pH (~ 9.0) the reaction may show $[\text{H}^+]$ dependence, but this may lead to base hydrolysis of the complex. Hence higher pH study is avoided. At low pH (~ 2.0) when the reaction will show pH dependence, the reaction becomes very slow.

Table 2. Effect of $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ and temperature on the rate of the electron transfer reaction between $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ and DL-methionine

$[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$		$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$			
$10^3 [\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ (mol dm^{-3})	20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C	
8.4	1.26 (1.5)	2.34 (2.78)	5.25 (6.25)	10.0 (11.9)	
9.8	1.38 (1.41)	2.69 (2.74)	6.02 (6.14)	11.17 (11.94)	
11.2	1.45 (1.3)	2.88 (2.57)	6.61 (5.90)	12.9 (11.52)	
12.6	1.66 (1.32)	3.51 (2.79)	7.24 (5.75)	14.1 (11.19)	
14.0	1.95 (1.4)	3.8 (2.71)	7.94 (5.67)	15.5 (11.07)	

$10^2 k_2 (\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$ 1.39 ± 0.08 2.72 ± 0.09 5.94 ± 0.25 11.52 ± 0.4
 $\Delta H^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1}) = 106 \pm 3$
 $\Delta S^\ddagger (\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}) = 75.7 \pm 10$

Data in the parenthesis are the corresponding second order rate constants (k_2).

Effect of $[\text{DL-methionine}]$ on reaction rate : The effect of varying $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ on the reaction rate was studied at fixed pH and between 20 to 35°C . At fixed $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the concentration of $10^3 [\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ was varied from 8.4 to 14.0 mol dm^{-3} . The results are collected in Table 2. It is observed that as $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ increases, the k_{obs} increases in a linear fashion (Fig. 2). This indicates that the order of the reaction with respect

to $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ is one.

Fig. 1. Repetitive spectral scan of $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ and DL-methionine : (1) $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $\text{pH} = 4.5$ and 30°C , (2) $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $\text{pH} = 4.5$ and 30°C and at 0 h, (3) 1 h, (4) 2.5 h and (5) 24 h.

Effect of solvent on reaction rate : With $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}} = 8.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.5$, $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$, the $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) changed from 5.25 to 7.10 when HAc was varied from 0 to 40% (v/v) (see Table 1). The increase in rate with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium indicates that species involved in the reaction have either same charge or is a case of reaction between charged species and uncharged species. The above reaction is an example of reaction between charged species and neutral molecule.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate : The reactions were studied at four different temperatures from 20 to 35°C

Fig. 2. The linear plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{DL-methionine}]_{\text{T}}$ at 20 to 35°C .

Fig. 3. (A) Protolytic equilibria of DL-methionine and (B) oxidation of DL-methionine by $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ to DL-methionine sulfoxide.

$^{\circ}\text{C}$, with constant $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ with varying DL-methionine concentration from 8.4×10^{-3} to $14.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $\text{pH} = 4.5$. The second order rate constants ($10^2 k_2$) changed from 1.39 ± 0.08 to $11.52 \pm 0.4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The $10^2 k_2$ at 25°C was found to be $2.72 \pm 0.09 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The values of ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} were calculated using Eyring equation. The values of ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} are $106 \pm 3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $75.7 \pm 10 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 2). The high positive value of ΔS^{\ddagger} indicates the reaction to be outer sphere.

Stoichiometry and characterisation of the product : The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by keeping $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}]_{\text{T}}$ constant at $2.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and varying the concentration of DL-methionine from 8.4×10^{-3} to $14.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at $\text{pH} = 4.5$. After 24 h $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{6-}]$ was analysed spectrophotometrically at 624 nm. The stoichiometry was found to be 2 moles of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{6-}$ per mole of DL-methionine.

A method²⁴ for the characterization of the product was employed by adding an acetone-ethanol mixture (1 : 1 volume ratio) to a reaction mixture containing $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{6-}$ and DL-methionine in a molar proportion of 1 : 7 which had previously been brought to $\text{pH} = 4.0$. The solution was left for evaporation at room temperature in a vacuum desiccator for few days. Fine light green colored crystals of the product appeared which was washed with ethanol and dried by keeping in a desiccator.

IR spectra of the product were recorded in a Shimadzu FTIR-8000 spectrophotometer. In the product most of the

peaks of DL-methionine were retained. A broad strong NH_3^+ stretching band appeared at 3390.6 cm^{-1} in the product compared to that at 2916.2 cm^{-1} in DL-methionine. The shift to higher frequency is probably due to association of water with the product. A strong peak at 1568 cm^{-1} and a weak peak at 1409.9 cm^{-1} are obtained in the product^{25,26} due to absorption of carboxylate group. The corresponding peaks in DL-methionine are obtained at 1581.5 and 1413.7 cm^{-1} respectively. A new strong peak appears at 1109 cm^{-1} in the product which is probably due to $\text{S}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration. The corresponding peak of sulfoxides is obtained in the $1070\text{--}1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. From the individual assignment of different peaks, it can be inferred that the product is methionine sulfoxide, the structure of which is shown in Fig. 3B.

Experimental

The $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ was prepared by the reported method¹⁴ and characterised spectrophotometrically²⁷ (at 388 nm , $\epsilon_{388} = 1150 \pm 2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The chemicals used were of A.R. grade and doubly distilled water was used through out the process. The electron transfer reaction was studied at $\text{pH} = 4.5 \pm 0.01$ using a prestandardised Elico (India) digital pH meter equipped with glass electrode.

On mixing DL-methionine with $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{5-}$ solution there is decrease of absorbance at 390 nm with simultaneous increase in absorbance at 624 nm at the same pH. An increase in absorbance at 624 nm (with low $\epsilon_{624} = 180 \pm 2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates the formation of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{W}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{6-}$. The change in absorbance of the mixture at different time intervals is found to show a broad isobestic region at about $500 \pm 20 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 1).

The absorbance measurements for kinetic studies were done using a Systronic 119 PC scanning spectrophotometer. Reaction progress was monitored at 390 nm . Pseudo-first-order conditions were maintained through out the runs by using a large excess (>10 -fold) of DL-methionine. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained from the slopes of $\ln(A_t - A_{\infty})$ versus t plots.

$$\ln(A_t - A_{\infty}) = k_{\text{obs}} t + c \quad (2)$$

where A_t and A_{∞} are the absorbances of the reaction mixture at time t and at equilibrium respectively. The reported rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The correlation coefficient of plots used to determine k_{obs} were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

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